

STUDY OF DEGRADATION IN THE PERFORMANCE OF PV PANEL AND SHADING EFFECT

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Abstract—Photovoltaic (PV) integration in buildings, telecommunication stations, power plants, and industrial uses has increased dramatically over the previous decade, in an effort to provide cheaper and cleaner energy generation and energy savings. The output power of a solar energy system is determined by solar radiation and the temperature of the PV panel's surface. The goal of this study is to illustrate that dust shadowing reduces solar radiation, which lowers PV panel output power. As a result, dust shadowing is a crucial consideration when planning and installing a solar system. Current mismatch occurs when a solar cell is completely shaded. Due to the current imbalance, the PV panel heats up in hotspots. If the heating is kept on for a long time, the solar cell crystal might be irreversibly damaged, reducing the life of the PV panel. We'll look at the consequences of them and analyze Efficiency of PV panel , maximum power point tracking, PV panel performance under shading effect, effect of Temperature on PV Panel Performance.

Keywords: Short Circuit Current; Temperature; Solar Irradiance; PV panel; Shading effect.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Introduction:

In contrast to fossil fuels, the sun has more than enough energy to supply the entire world's energy demands, and it won't run out anytime soon. The sole constraint on solar energy as a renewable resource is our capacity to efficiently and economically convert it to electricity. When one uses solar energy, no ozone-depleting substances are released into the atmosphere. The solar energy resource is vast. The US Department of Energy estimates that the quantity of sunlight that reaches the surface of the globe in an hour and a half is sufficient to provide all of the world's energy needs for a whole year. The energy contained in all of the world's reserves of coal, oil, and natural gas is equivalent to just 18 days of sunshine on Earth. Additionally, the fuel is free once a mechanism is in place to harness the solar resource and transform it into usable energy. Solar energy has a far smaller ecological impact

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than other methods of power generation since it is an endless source of CO₂-free energy.

Solar radiation (kWh/m²/day) and area of Bangladesh with highest potential for solar energy utilization

Fig: Solar Radiation [34]

The impact is mostly linked to the creation and distribution of the special materials and metals needed to produce solar panels. In many parts of the globe today, renewable energies in particular, wind and solar energy are less expensive than conventional ones. The fundamental renewable energy sources, including wind and solar photovoltaic, are lowering their prices dramatically, making them completely competitive with traditional sources in an increasing number of places. Renewable energy is already the most sustainable option for providing the globe with electricity, both ecologically and economically, thanks to economies of scale and innovation. The household solar energy schemes in Bangladesh are among the biggest in the world. The World Bank and other international development agencies, the business sector, and the government are collaborating to provide accessible, low-cost solar electricity in areas where the conventional grid is inaccessible. Around 20 million individuals in rural regions, or nearly one-eighth of the country's population, now have access to energy thanks to small-scale solar home systems. This number of houses and persons is higher than the national average. In addition, the initiative has implemented 13 solar mini-grids and 1,000 solar irrigation pumps. The National Solar Energy Roadmap

2021–2041 (draft) explains the present state of solar energy development and goals. To utilize this energy effectively, the government has launched many projects. 90% of Bangladesh's population currently has access to electricity, with a per-person energy production rate of about 464kwh. Up till October 2019, the public and private sectors completed and are operating about 62 off-network rooftop solar projects with a generating capacity of 14.36 MW and 50 on-grid projects with a generation capacity of 26.45 MW. RMG is Bangladesh's largest export industry, and by 2021, it hopes to transact \$50 billion in goods. Bangladesh can create 635 MW (17.3%) from solar rooftops, and the yearly output will be 860 GWh, which would decrease about 576,200 tons of CO₂ emissions. The government has launched a "500 MW Solar Power Mission" to support the administration's Power System Master Plan (PSMP). The production of photovoltaic panels is subject to various climatic factors, including wind speed, humidity, temperature, precipitation, solar radiation, etc. As a tropical nation, Bangladesh has two significant climatic variations: the monsoon season, which lasts from June to September, and the western wave disturbance, which causes light rains in southern parts throughout the winter. Days during this season are overcast, and frequent heavy downpours become the usual. A new phenomenon known as "smog" has afflicted the atmosphere as a result of global warming and the burning of rice root stubbles and straws throughout the winter, which reduces the brightness of the sun's rays during the winter season. The performance of solar PV panels strongly depends on the solar radiation falling on them. Shading affects the amount of solar radiation falling on the panel surface. In this paper, the effect of light intensity is overlooked. The factors discussed in what follows include time, temperature, and open-circuit (OC) voltage. Knowing that time is related to temperature but not having a particular quantity to relate it, two experiments were conducted to study the effect of shading over time and another under a certain temperature regime. The primary objective was to explore the shading effect on PV cells to determine the degree to which it would degrade and how serious a problem cell shading is. In addition, it is important to understand issues like series, parallel, and series-parallel shading.

B. Problem Statement:

Air pollution or greenhouse gases are not produced by solar energy systems or power plants. When solar energy replaces or lessens the usage of other energy sources with greater environmental impacts, it can have a beneficial, indirect impact on the environment. Fossil fuel use raises atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide and methane, which exacerbates the greenhouse effect and causes our planet to warm more quickly than before. As a result, as sea levels rise and glaciers melt, a variety of calamities like tornadoes, frequent flooding, excessive heat, and drought are brought on. On the other side, using solar power to generate energy results in no greenhouse gas emissions, which helps to halt climate change. It costs nothing to operate and uses no fuel to convert sunlight into energy using the photovoltaic process.

Additionally, a lot of researchers and students are working harder now because of the rise in energy demand and the dependability of solar energy. In such situation, several research and development efforts are underway to further this sector. To gain a better understanding of how solar energy is used, researchers are working on these. A large number of books and thesis papers have been published in prominent conferences and publications. The future of this solar, the design, various theoretical findings based on projects and study, and actual investigations are constantly enlarging the area of solar energy. Solar PV energy is dependable and secure; it creates no noise or pollution, is less constrained, fails less frequently, and needs no maintenance. In order to solve the worsening energy problems and environmental degradation, it is essential. Every nation in the world has put more effort into developing PV power generation since the 1970s energy crisis; examples of this include China's Bright Project for Western Provinces Without Electricity, Japan's Sunshine Program, Germany's Million Solar Roofs Program, and the United States' Million Solar Roofs Initiative[1].

Bangladesh has a number of renewable energy sources, but because of its location, solar energy is the most practical option. The average daily solar radiation varies from 4-6.5 kWh/m² with a lovely sunny hour throughout the year. This experiment and data collection were done on the solar panels at the Institute of Energy, University of Dhaka, Dhaka1000 (90°33' E longitude and 23°77' N latitude). Two sets of panels—one monocrystalline and the other polycrystalline—were selected for the scurrility. The arrays have a predetermined latitude tilt angle and are pointed south. On March 6, 2020, the efficiency decrease for monocrystalline pair (M1 and M2) and polycrystalline couple (M3 and M4) panels is 27.17 % and 20%, respectively. The efficiency and performance ratios of clean and dirty panels are now equivalent as a result of the rain on February 14, 2020. The dusty panel performance ratios have drastically declined by the end of February 2020. After the experiment, it was shown that efficiency falls as temperature rises and as the amount of dust on the surface of PV solar panels grows. PV solar panels lose a significant amount of their efficiency as the temperature exceeds 40°C. Due to the high levels of pollution in the city, cleaning solar photovoltaic panels has become a significant issue in Dhaka[2].

Photovoltaic modules with dust on them have decreased transmittance, which lowers the amount of effective solar insolation reaching them, reducing their efficiency. Studies show that dust or tiny particles are affected by a variety of factors, including dust characteristics, exposure time, site climate, wind speed, and tilt angle of the solar collector. Since soiling may reduce transmission by up to 40%, it can cause significant loss. An everyday cleaning cycle is suggested in regions with significant levels of dust. Low-latitude locales should have a daily cleaning cycle despite having a moderate dust density because of their lower tilt angle, which leads to increased dust deposition. The tilt angle will be mild in mid-latitude 5 areas, resulting in lower rates of dust buildup and just weekly cleaning. In high

latitude areas, dust won't be a significant problem due of panel[3].

Dust storms directly affect solar radiation, which in turn affects how well solar energy plants work. Depending on how distant a place is from the active dust sources in the area, the impact of dust storms on PV energy systems varies dramatically. Two instances of 48-hour-old dust cloud impacts on two PV testing sites were looked into. The data showed a broad range of fluctuation when compared to the day before the dust struck, with the power output altering by anywhere between 14.4% and 37.0% [4].

Solar photovoltaic panel performance may be greatly impacted by shading. Although it is obvious that the best option is to completely avoid shading—which isn't always possible due to things like clouds, rain, etc.—many people are unaware that even if a small portion of a solar photovoltaic panel is in shade, the performance of the entire panel will be significantly reduced. This is due to the fact that solar photovoltaic panels are really made up of a number of solar photovoltaic cells connected in series. The power output of the entire system in series is thereby decreased to the level of current flowing through the weakest cell when the power output of a single cell is drastically reduced. Therefore, even a little bit of shading may drastically affect how well your complete system of solar photovoltaic panels performs [5]. The partial shadowing on solar systems is one of the primary sources of losses in energy output (PV modules). These photovoltaic (PV) modules are made up of parallel or serially linked photovoltaic (PV) cells with variously arranged diodes. A PV cell's curve changes according to the radiation it receives [5][6] and its temperature. Additionally, the modules feature diodes that, when enough cells are shaded or broken, allow the electricity to travel down a different channel. Two common bypass diode arrangements are [7] overlapped (Fig. 1a) and no-overlapped (Fig. 1b). It should be emphasized that because there may be several channels for current flow, the analysis in modules with overlapping diodes is more difficult. This study investigates the unique behavior of a PV module and a photovoltaic array (PV array) of PV modules that are both linked to an inverter and experience shadows. In the past, much research has been done on the effects of partial shade on PV systems [8][9]. Some earlier research introduced the idea of the shading factor by assuming that the drop in power generation is proportionate to the shaded area and decrease in solar irradiation. While this idea is valid for a single cell, at the module or array level, the power decline is frequently nonlinear with the shaded region [10]. Other earlier research frequently include intricate methods that are challenging for someone with little background in electronic/solid-state physics to understand [11]. The primary goal of this paper is to explain how shading affects solar panel performance in very straightforward language that a power engineer or PV system designer may easily understand. A review of a PV cell's I-V curve and circuit model comes first. The effect of partial shading on the I-V and P-V curves of a circuit consisting of two cells with and without bypass diodes is then discussed, in addition to other topics.

Fig: Bypass diodes (a) overlapped (b) no-overlapped [35]
Source: Applied Energy 86 (2009)

C. Aims:

The main goal of this research is to investigate the effects of climatic factors on solar modules as well as the effects of shading on the energy output of solar modules. This study's primary goals were to investigate the impacts of environmental factors on solar modules and the effects of shadowing on their ability to produce electricity. Short circuit current is the output parameter of solar modules, and environmental factors include temperature, wind speed, humidity, barometric pressure, and sun surface radiation. Because of diverse trees, clouds, surrounding buildings, dust, and other light-blocking obstructions, there is shade. The shadowing caused by buildings in Bangladesh is both the most significant aspect and the major issue of this article. Bangladesh's population is growing every day, which has a tremendous impact on the building industry. So, how can we prevent these issues is our key worry. As the population grows, the environment changes rapidly, creating hazardous shadowing effects for solar panels. The Bangladeshi population is seen in Fig. 3[12]

Fig: 1.3 Bangladesh Population

D. Brief Methodology

Considering that the total projected load is 915 KW. To choose additional parts, such the inverter, effectively and efficiently, we must convert the power in kilowatts to the kilovolt-ampere (KVA). It is converted using the formula below.

KVA is equal to KW/0.8, therefore 915KW/0.8 equals 1192.75VA, or around 1.5KVA. The sizes and capacities of the system's components were established based on the anticipated loads, and are displayed in Table

Table : System Components and Capacity[35]

S/N	EQUIPMENT	QUANTITY	CAPACITY PER EQUIPMENT	COMBINED CAPACITY
1.	SOLAR PANEL	(19*8)	915 WATT	915 WATTS(24 V)
2.	CHARGE CONTROLLER	1	20 AMPS/24 V	20 AMPS/24 V
3.	DEEP CYCLE BATTERY	2	200AH, 12 V	200AH, 24 V
4.	INVERTER	1	1.5 KVA (24/220V)	1.5 KVA (24V/220V)

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Introduction

The transition from the extraction of energy from non-renewable resources to renewable resources is virtually complete. For the purposes of this project, solar energy among all renewable resources are efficiently and conveniently extracted. The following thesis work is entitled as, “Study of degradation in the performance of PV panel and shading effect”, which requires a clear understanding of the theoretical fundamentals of the solar module. Consequently, the theoretical review of the solar panel in this chapter is centered on the impact of various weather conditions on energy output.

First, a brief description of a solar module's operation is given, along with information on related metrics including short circuit current (I_{sc}), open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), ideality factor, fill factor, power, and energy. The solar cell from the IV, PV characteristics curve is equivalent to the aforementioned parameters. Later on, it is explained how drastically different predicted energy outputs from solar modules result from variations in meteorological characteristics including humidity, wind speed, air pressure, and temperature. Additionally, the crucial impact of solar irradiance (W/m^2) on the output power of the solar module is demonstrated.

B. Solar Panel

B.1 Basic of Solar Panel

By capturing sunlight and using it as a power source, solar energy is a potential solution to the current climate concerns and dependence on fossil fuels. Solar energy mostly comes from the sun. The sun's mostly photon-based energy is transformed by solar panels into electricity. A solar panel, also known as a PV device, is a semiconductor that transforms solar energy into electrical current. Solar cells are nothing more than p-n junctions as they are made of layers of silicon, phosphorous, and boron. PV devices are

combinations of many different types of solar cells. Positive charge is provided by boron, whereas negative charge is provided by silicon and phosphorous.

When a photon impacts the PV panel's surface, it knocks out the electrons in their atomic orbit and releases them into the electric field that is created by the PV cells dragging these liberated electrons in a directed current. Like a battery, solar cells have two layers: a positive layer and a negative layer, which together provide an electric field. This entire process is known as the "Photovoltaic Effect." When sunlight strikes the solar panel surface, the cells take in the photons from the energy and produce an electric current.

In the electric field produced by the solar cells, the energy from the photons that impact the solar panel's surface causes the electrons to be liberated from their atomic orbits. As a result, free electrons are drawn out in the directed current.

Table 2.1: Advantages and Disadvantages of the Mono-crystalline, Polycrystalline, Thin-film Solar Panel

Solar panel type	Advantages	Disadvantages
PERC	Higher efficiency than (5%) Mono-crystalline	Costly
Mono-crystalline	High efficiency , over 20%	Costly
Polycrystalline	Low price	Lower efficiency 15-17%
Thin-film	Portable and flexible Low weight	Lowest efficiency 2-3% less than crystalline silicon

Crystalline solar panels are the most efficient among all panel kinds, but they are also the priciest[37].

B.2 How Do Solar Panels Work?

Sun is a new clear reactor. It produces photons, which are tiny energy particles. A solar cell is struck by photons from the sun when a solar panel is in the sun. Atomic electrons became excited and broke free. Electricity is created by connecting the positive and negative sides of a photovoltaic device's cells in a circuit to an electrical source. Solar cells in a PV device are carefully designed with positively and negatively charged semiconductors placed together to produce an electric field. The drooping electrons are given a route by this electric field, which forces them to go in that direction toward the conductive metal plates.[13]

B.3 Mechanism of Solar Panel

The semiconductor materials used to make solar cells must have a bandgap close to 1.5 eV, like silicon. In terms of electricity flowing, there are probably three different sorts of materials: semiconductors, insulators, and conductors. A

conductor has no band gaps between the valence and conduction bands, which makes it possible for an electron to move smoothly between atoms when the appropriate voltage is applied. Then there are certain substances known as insulators that do not conduct electricity. A excellent illustration of that substance is plastic. On the other hand, semiconductor materials exhibit both conductor and insulator properties. They only let the passage of free electrons under certain circumstances. The way that the electrons in atoms are arranged is known as a band.

Fig: 2.1 insulators-conductors-semiconductors

Source:engineeringtutorial.com/insulators-conductors-semiconductors/

It is evident from the preceding graphic that an insulator has an extremely high band gap, which prevents electrons from passing through. Since the band gap overlaps in a conductor, moving an electron through it is quite simple. Band gaps in semiconductors are smaller in insulators and larger in conductors. Therefore, given the right circumstances, the band gap in this type of material may be closed by applying enough energy, allowing the valance electron to migrate. Two distinct varieties of silicon are used to make solar cells. Silicon has a band gap of 1.12ev. [14]

When sunlight strikes a solar panel deeply, the p-n junction allows light photons to pass through the extremely thin p-type layer with ease. The energy required to create many electron-hole pairs is provided by the energy of photons. The thermal balance of the connection is upset by the incoming light. Free electrons from the depletion zone quickly cross the junction's n-type side at this period. On the other hand, the p-type side of the junction has holes that are still present in the depletion zone. Free electrons are prevented from crossing the junction whenever the n-type side is holding them due to the barrier potential. In a same manner, freType equation here.shly formed holes are unable to cross the junction's barrier potential. With time, the n-type side of the junction's electron concentration rises while the p-type side's hole concentration rises. P-n junction thus behaves like a little battery cell. A voltage known as photo voltage is

created. A little load can be crossed by a smaller current using the junction[15].

Fig: 2.2 Solar Cell Mechanism [36]

B.4 Solar Cell Characteristics

Single Diode Model

We will briefly discuss the single diode model, the I-V characteristics, and the electrical properties of a PV array in three sections. To begin with, all of the solar cell models that are currently available share a single diode model. The model consists of a diode, a series of power loss models R_S , a shunt resistance, and a regulated current source photo generated IPH to represent the single source Shockley equation.

Figure-2.3: Equivalent circuit of five-parameter model of a solar cell [16]

After then, a link between the current and voltage I-V characteristic is required in order to visually portray the operation of a PV cell. To build a system that operates in its optimal electrical outlet, the curve's presented information is crucial.

$$I = I_0 [(qVnKT) - 1] - IL$$

Here,

- I_0 = dark saturation current
- q = charge
- V = applied voltage
- n = ideality factor
- k = Boltzmann's constant
- T = temperature
- IL = light generated current

Graphical representation of I-V characteristics curve is given below:

Fig.: IV curve of a solar module showing the open-circuit voltage[17]

$$V_{oc} = \frac{n \cdot K \cdot T \cdot N_s}{q} \ln\left(\frac{I_{sc}}{I_0}\right)$$

Here,

- q = charge
- k = Boltzmann's constant
- n = ideality factor
- N_s = number of cells connected in series in the panel
- T = temperature in kelvin

Fig:I-V Characteristics curve of the Solar panel

Fig: I-V Characteristics graphs

The rating of the solar cell depends on cell parameters like:

a. Open Circuit Voltage (OCV): This phrase describes the array's maximum output voltage when the terminals are open, which implies they are not connected to any sources. Voltage of an open circuit, or VOC. This value often depends on how many PV panels are linked in series.[18]

b. Short Circuit Current: This is the amount of current the solar panel can produce at its maximum when the output connections are shorted (a situation known as a short circuit) or when there is no voltage across the solar cell. ISC, or short circuit current, stands for. In general, the value is more than the operating current. [18]

c. Fill Factor (FF): The relationship between the maximum power that an array can deliver under typical operating conditions and the product of open circuit voltage and short circuit current (VOC ISC) is known as the fill factor. This is the fundamental concept of the array's quality. The fill factor typically ranges from 0.7 to 0.8. [18]

$$FF = \frac{P_{mp}}{(V_{oc} \cdot I_{oc})}$$

$$P_{mp} = V_{mp} \cdot I_{mp}$$

Here ,

- V_{mp} = maximum voltage and
- I_{mp} = maximum current
- V_{oc} = open circuit voltage
- I_{oc} = open circuit current

d. Maximum Power Point: This refers to the point at which the array's power delivered to the load reaches its maximum value. It is noted by MPP, where

$$MPP = V_{MP} \times I_{MP}$$

e. Ideality Factor: Ideality factor is denoted by n and it is one of the diodes I-V characteristics parameters. Therefore,

the ideality factor 15 of a diode is a measure of how closely the diode follows the ideal diode equation. For ideal case ideality factor $n=1$ but in non ideal case, it is more than 1. The equation of the ideality factor is given below

$$n = \frac{(V_{oc1} - V_{oc2}) * q}{k * T * N_s * \ln \left(\frac{I_{sc1}}{I_{sc2}} \right)}$$

Here;

- q = charge
- k = Boltzmann's constant
- N_s = number of cells

V_{OC1} & V_{OC2} = open-circuit voltage

I_{SC1} & I_{SC2} = short circuit current

f. Reverse Saturation Current: It is a measure of the leakage of carriers across the p-n junction. The reverse saturation current denoted as I_o . Equation of the reverse saturation current is given below;

$$I = \frac{I_{sc}}{e^{\left(\frac{V_{oc} * q}{n * k * T * N_s} \right)}}$$

Here;

- q = charge
- k = Boltzmann's constant
- n = ideality factor
- N_s = number of cells

T = temperature in kelvin

I_{sc} = short circuit current

V_{oc} = open circuit voltage

B.5 Weather parameters effects on the performance of PV solar module:

Unusually, the carbon emissions needed to create power are rising. The cleaner and more dependable energy source for the future that will help to slow global warming appears to be solar energy. Since the sun is the primary source of solar energy, the weather in the area where the solar panel is located also has an impact on its production. Numerous weather-related factors can influence how well a solar cell performs. The output of the solar panel is impacted by temperature, wind speed, humidity, and air pressure. In our forecasting model, we used PVSYS 7.3 to get data on humidity, air pressure, wind speed, and temperature. We are providing a brief overview of such weather effects in this section.

Fig: Weather parameter graph

B.6 Effect of Temperature

The term "irradiance" refers to the measurement of the power density of sunlight that is received at a point on Earth. It calculated its wattage per square meter. Irradiance, to put it another way, is a measurement of the energy density of sunshine. The output of solar panels can alter depending on changes in temperature and sun irradiation. Solar irradiance has an impact on both the fill factor and solar cell efficiency. The I-V and P-V properties are also impacted by the daytime variations in solar isolation. Both the open circuit voltage and the short circuit current fall when the sun irradiation decreases [19]. However, in order to determine the quantity of irradiance from the direct sunlight observed by the solar panel—which is crucial for calculating solar energy—we must take into account several features such as azimuth angle, latitude, solar altitude, and declination angle.

B.6 Solar Altitude:

This phrase describes the angle formed between the beam of the sun and a horizontal plane. Degrees are used to measure it. The sun zenith angle and solar height are connected. The angle between the vertical and the sun's beam is known as the zenith angle. The time of day, season, and earth's altitude all have an impact on the value of solar altitude. Greater solar height is found near the equator than it is towards the poles of the globe [20]. The equation below can be used to determine the solar height.

$$\alpha = \sin^{-1}(\sin \delta * \sin \varphi + \cos \delta * \cos \varphi * \cos \omega)$$

Here,

- Hour of the angle = ω
- Declination angle = δ
- Latitude angle = φ

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Introduction:

Solar energy is directly converted to electricity using photovoltaic (PV) cells. They operate in all weather, but when the sun is shining brightly and directly on the PV cells, more power is generated. The solar cell serves as the fundamental unit of PV technology. The PV cell is made up of two or more layers of silicon or another semi-conducting material. Electrical charges are created when the silicon is exposed to light and can be carried away by metal contacts as direct currents (DC). Since a single PV cell can only provide a tiny amount of electricity, many PV cells are linked together and protected by the glass to create the SOLAR PANEL module. You can generate power with PV without using gasoline, noise, or air pollution. Most PVs last 25 to 50 year. Electricity for telecommunications, telemetry, water pumping, lighting, television, DC refrigeration, and other low-power non-heating applications may be generated using solar energy in rural regions. Heating devices including kettles, toasters, stoves, geysers, and heaters use excessive amounts of energy, and consequently, it cannot be applied to a solar system. The solar panel, charge controller, battery, inverter, wiring, and associated loads are the system's fundamental parts. In this chapter, the application of PVsyst 7.3 Simulink on the collected data and the predicted output result will be discussed. To construct a 50kw solar power plant and determine how much solar energy can be converted into electrical energy at a certain site or location, we utilized the energy modeling application PVSYST.

B. Methods and Materials

We utilized the PC software program PVsyst 7.3 to research, size, and analyze data on entire PV systems. It covers grid-connected, standalone, pumping, and DC-grid (public transportation) PV systems and has vast information on metro systems and PV system parts in addition to generic tools for solar energy. To evaluate the impact of shade on PV panels, a research was conducted. To do so, we utilized pvsyst 7.33 to monitor the constant solar radiation of 1000 W/m² maintained throughout the study. For this investigation, 335Wp polycrystalline solar PV panels were employed.

Fig: IV curve corresponding Irradiance

Inverter:

One of a solar energy system's most crucial components is an inverter. It is a device that changes the power produced by solar panels from direct current (DC) to alternating current (AC), which is used by the electrical grid.

Inverter - Solar Inverter RPI M50A			
Manufacturer	Generic		
Model	Solar Inverter RPI M50A		
Commercial data			
Availability :	Prod. Since 2014	Data source :	Manufacturer 2014
Remarks			
		Sizes	
Technology:		Width	612 mm
Protection: IP65		Height	740 mm
Control: Display operational data		Depth	278 mm
DC power unbalance 60/40%		Weight	70.00 kg
Numbers of DC inputs must be checked before ordering			
Input characteristics (PV array side)			
Operating mode	MPPT		
Minimum MPP Voltage (Vmin)	200 V	Nominal PV Power (Pnom DC)	50 kW
Maximum MPP Voltage (Vmax)	800 V	Maximum PV Power (Pmax DC)	63 kW
Absolute max. PV Voltage (Vmax array)	1000 V	Power Threshold (Pthresh.)	40 W
Min. Voltage for PNom (Vmin@Pnom)	520 V		
"String" inverter with input protections		Multi MPPT capability	
Number of string inputs	12	Number of MPPT inputs	2
Behaviour at Vmin/Vmax	Limitation		
Behaviour at Pnom	Limitation		
Output characteristics (AC grid side)			
Grid voltage (Imax)	Triphased 230 V	Nominal AC Power (Pnom AC)	50 kWac
Grid frequency	50/60 Hz	Maximum AC Power (Pmax AC)	55 kWac
		Nominal AC current (Inom AC)	73 A
		Maximum AC current (Imax AC)	80 A

Efficiency defined for 3 voltages

	Maximum efficiency	European average efficiency
	%	%
Low voltage	97.9	97.5
Medium voltage	98.6	98.4
High voltage	98.1	97.9

C.MPPT (Maximum Power Point Tracking)

Under some circumstances, the Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) method is typically employed to extract the maximum available power from the PV cells. Maximum Power Point refers to the highest power that may be obtained from a PV module at a certain voltage. With variations in solar cell temperature, radiation, and terrain temperature, the maximum power changes. When MPPT examines the PV module's output, it determines how much power from the PV panel must be sent to the battery in order to charge it. In essence, it is a battery charge controller that controls buck-boost converters. These converters increase the PV panel's reduced voltage when there is shade, making the method workable and viable.

Fig: One Line Diagram

D. Design Specifications. Standards and Constraints

The equivalent circuit of PV cell is represented below in fig. 3.4 PV cell is vital innovation, which is introduced to convert solar energy into electrical energy with a PN junction semiconductor devices. Myriads of models have been designed to study PV system beneath the normal and partial shading conditions. PV cell holds a current source in parallel with a diode, shunt and series resistance. Standard equations provide the characteristics of the designed PV cell. The PV module designed by using pvsyst7.3 Simulink model contains 152 solar cells merged in series parallel configuration provides an open circuit voltage of 45.9V and short circuit current of 9.41A. The designed model is simulated and verified under linear near shading conditions. In standard condition (1000 W/m² and 25°C) the maximum power acquired 336.3 W. Fig. 3.4 represents the cell equivalent circuit.

Fig. 3.4 PV cell Equivalent circuit

The PV module that has been used technical specifications of that PV panel are being discussed below:

PV module - AE 335P6-72			
Manufacturer	Generic	Commercial data	
Model	AE 335P6-72	Availability:	Prod. Since 2022
		Data source:	Manufacturer 2020
Phnom STC power (manufacturer)	335 Wp	Technology	Si-poly
Module size (W x L)	0.992 x 1.956 m ²	Rough module area (A module)	1.94 m ²
Number of cells	1 x 72	Sensitive area (cells) (A cells)	1.75 m ²
Specifications for the model (manufacturer or measurement data)			
Reference temperature (T Ref)	25 °C	Reference irradiance (GRef)	1000 W/m ²
Open circuit voltage (Voc)	45.9 V	Short-circuit current (Isc)	9.41 A
Max. power point voltage (Vmpp)	37.1 V	Max. power point current (Impp)	9.04 A
=> maximum power (Pmp)	334.9 W	Isc temperature coefficient (mutsc)	5.0 mA/°C
One-diode model parameters			
Shunt resistance (R shunt)	550 Ω	Diode saturation current (IoRef)	0.136 nA
Series resistance (R series)	0.28 Ω	Voc temp. coefficient (MuVoc)	-153 mV/°C
Specified Pmax temper. coeff (mu Pmax R)	-0.40 %/°C	Diode quality factor (Gamma)	1.00
		Diode factor temper. coeff. (muGamma)	0.000 1/°C
Reverse Bias Parameters, for use in behavior of PV arrays under partial shadings or mismatch			
Reverse characteristics (dark) (BRRev)	3.20 mA/V ²	(quadratic factor per cell)	
Number of by-pass diodes per module	3	Direct voltage of by-pass diodes	-0.7 V
Model results for standard conditions (STC: T=25 °C, G=1000 W/m ² , AM=1.5)			
Max. power point voltage (Vmpp)	37.8 V	Max. power point current (Impp)	8.92 A
Maximum power (Pmpp)	336.3 Wp	Power temper. coefficient (mu Pmpp)	-0.40 %/°C
Efficiency (I Module area) (Eff_mod)	17.3 %	Fill factor (FF)	0.778
Efficiency (I Cells area) (Eff_cells)	19.2 %		

E. Near shadings parameter

Perspective of the PV-field and surrounding shading scene

Fig: PV-field and surrounding shading scene

F. System Analysis

Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems create energy using the photovoltaic effect, which occurs when sunlight knocks electrons loose in the silicon materials that make up solar PV cells. As a result, anytime a solar cell or panel does not get sunlight owing to shade or surrounding impediments, the entire system generates less total solar power. This is known as PV system shadow loss. Shading can originate from a number of sources, including: Buildings, trees, antennas, and poles in the vicinity "self-shade" from other PV panel rows. The landscape around the installation location provides horizontal shade. Other considerations include panel orientation, soiling, and differential aging.

In his book, [Renewable Energy and Efficient Electric Power Systems](#), Stanford University's Gil Masters demonstrates how shading just one out of 36 cells in a small solar module can reduce total power output by as much as 75%. To see why shading causes such high losses, consider water running via pipes. For a given irradiance level, the flow rate of water through the pipe is constant, much as the current through a cell string is constant.

Fig: String of Solar Cell

As installers, we may employ a variety of solar design solutions to prevent shading losses. Among these are various stringing arrangements, bypass diodes, and module-level power electronics (MLPEs)

In this study, we developed a PV module and then investigated various forms of shading losses. We also informed you of the daily input output diagram and predicted system output distribution, complete with diagrams and graph analyses. Normalized output (per installed kWp) and performance ratio have also been provided [33].

G. Summary

This chapter discusses the materials and methods how it's design or it's specification, standards and constraints. Here we showing that the equivalent circuit of PV module and it is introduce to convert solar energy to electrical energy. For standards characteristics value the PV module designed by using pvsyst7.3 Simulink models that contains 152 solar cell. The short circuit current, I_{sc} , is predicted using a machine learning model (A). The length of the training dataset utilized to train the learning system is clearly indicated by the predicted $I_{sc}(A)$ findings. It has been shown that the algorithm performs better when trained on a dataset that includes more historical data. In comparison to the

experimental short circuit current $I_{sc}(A)$, the average percentage error rate was computed

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Results:

Current-voltage (I-V) and power-voltage (P-V) properties of polycrystalline PV panels, as well as their electrical responses such as current, voltage, and power under the aforementioned situations, were measured. I-V and P-V properties of polycrystalline PV panels are depicted in the figures below, respectively. These traits show a significant decline in PV performance

Fig: Mismatch loss statics

Graph analysis of Shading loss corresponding with beam linear and electrical loss:

Here Shading factor on linear is 0.495 and 0.741 according to module strings where sun azimuth is 63° . The beam linear loss is 1.8% and electrical loss is 11.7%.

From the analysis of the collector field graph using Pvsyst 7.3 array losses for $1000w/m^2$ Module quality loss is -0.7% where module mismatch loss is 2.4% and including other losses global loss is 15.5%.

Fig: ISO shading

Above iso shading diagram projects on different shading losses on different days depending on the availability of solar radiation. As we know 21 June is the biggest day and solar radiation is maximum on that day so shading loss on that day is the lowest. and 22 December is the smallest day so following the vice versa on that day shading loss is the maximum.

Degradation Loss

Effect of each loss on the array of characteristics

For given operating conditions (static loss values, not valid over a running period!)

External Operating Conditions

irradiation 1000 W/m² Wind Velocity 1.0 m/s

Beam/Global ratio 80 % Incidence Angle 40 °

Ambient Temper. 25 °C

Fig:: Degradation loss

Main Result

System Production 63424 kWh/year
Produced Energy

Specific production 1246 kWh/kWp/year

Performance Ratio PR 77.09 %

Fig: System and Specific production and performance

Balances and main results

	GlobHor kWh/m²	DiffHor kWh/m²	T_Amb °C	GlobInc kWh/m²	GlobEff kWh/m²	EArray kWh	E_Grid kWh	PR ratio
January	105.5	62.4	17.06	133.0	121.3	5546	5021	0.742
February	112.9	61.5	20.97	133.7	123.3	5480	5387	0.792
March	155.3	80.8	25.75	167.5	154.6	6706	6591	0.773
April	157.8	90.3	27.63	154.7	141.5	6143	6038	0.766
May	159.5	102.4	28.30	144.7	130.8	5737	5642	0.766
June	133.6	91.7	28.14	118.0	105.8	4676	4596	0.765
July	127.2	83.3	28.53	113.3	101.7	4466	4390	0.761
August	135.3	99.5	28.68	127.0	114.2	5047	4964	0.767
September	126.6	75.9	28.00	128.5	117.2	5107	5019	0.767
October	119.0	70.7	27.14	132.7	121.7	5308	5217	0.772
November	108.3	58.5	23.01	136.0	124.8	5528	5434	0.785
December	97.8	56.2	18.90	126.6	115.3	5213	5125	0.795
Year	1538.8	933.3	25.20	1615.7	1472.2	64958	63424	0.771

Fig: IV&PV curve

Legends

- GlobHor Global horizontal irradiation
- DiffHor Horizontal diffuse irradiation
- T_Amb Ambient Temperature
- GlobInc Global incident in coll. plane
- GlobEff Effective Global, corr. for IAM and shadings

- EArray Effective energy at the output of the array
- E_Grid Energy injected into grid
- PR Performance Ratio

Fig:PV curve corresponding Incident Irradiance

Predef. graphs
Daily Input/Output diagram

Fig: System output and power distribution

The performance of solar photovoltaic panels can be significantly impacted by shading. What many people don't realize is that even if a small portion of the solar photovoltaic panel is in shade, the performance of the entire solar photovoltaic panel will be significantly reduced. It is obvious that the best solution is to avoid shading altogether, though this isn't possible in practice due to factors like clouds, rain, etc. Here, in this chapter, discuss about result and this result shows some losses. Here we see shading loss in clear day 1.8% and at same time electrical loss 11.7% and its azimuth angle is 63° . Here current loss at fixed voltage 5.9%. In the main result PV Array losses shown in 0.93 kWh/kW/day and system loss 0.08 kWh/kWp/day and normal temperature array losses for $1000\text{w}/\text{m}^2$, the module loss is -0.7% and global loss is 15.5%. In iso-Shading diagram shown the full azimuths and all different days losses. Polycrystalline silicon (pc-Si), amorphous silicon (a-Si), and monocrystalline silicon (mc-Si) are examples of PV cell advancements that also illustrate the PV panels' erroneous performance. In the outdoor regime, several PV panel types reduce the system's electrical parameter. In this article, the performance of polycrystalline silicon panels is

examined. The outcome of the experiment confirmed the monocrystalline panel's output parameter. Under shadowing phenomena, mono-crystalline panels outperform other improvements in PV cells.

V. ECONOMICAL, SOCIETAL AND GLOBAL IMPACT

In the most recent technological period, there has been a growth in the need for energy, therefore solar energy has received a lot of attention in an effort to meet these demands. In the current study, we examined how shadowing affected the PV array in various scenarios. Partial shadow is the key factor impacting PV panel efficiency in open air settings. Partial shading reduces the amount of irradiation, which lowers short circuit current and output power significantly. At 30% shade, the maximum current is reduced by 1/3. The PV array converts solar energy into electrical energy, hence the electrical responsiveness of the PV panel is essential. The PV array converts solar energy into electrical energy, hence the electrical responsiveness of the PV panel is essential. Partial shadowing has inadequate effect on a PV panel's electrical response. Installations of bypass diodes have made a substantial contribution to mitigating these effects. The system's coherent current flow was created by the bypass diode, which also prevented reverse biased current from passing across the PV array. We can see the dispersion of irradianations in this image. At this temperature, the power ratio is 0.93 and the power array is 1.02. The average power of a PV array is 50.9 kw, while the maximum power for $1072\text{ w}/\text{m}^2$, 60°C is 46.7 kw. This indicates that if irradiation decreases, the production will as well.

Fig: Irradiation distribution of inverter

The PV panel is shielded from the risk of deterioration in this way. The construction of a method to improve the performance of PV arrays visible or prominent to shadowing is one of the study's possible applications. By adding data on the shading effect to the PV panel output parameters, an algorithm to decrease such negative effects of shading on the system may be constructed.

A. Environmental and Ethical Issues

Solar energy is a type of renewable energy and also the most accessible and cost-free renewable energy source for all nations. Solar power is the conversion of solar energy into electrical and thermal energy, which are two widely used forms of energy. In general, solar energy technology may convert solar energy into electrical energy into two primary groups [24,25]. One use is concentrating solar power (CSP) systems, which use hundreds of mirrors to focus sunlight to create heat or electricity at temperatures typically between 400 and 1000 °C. Additionally, CSP may function as a solar energy technology by storing heat or by combining with fossil-fueled power plants like natural gas and oil power plants to provide electricity when the sun is not shining [26]. A large-scale, commercially feasible, and economically viable method of producing energy is CSP. In order to concentrate solar energy and power conventional steam turbines or engines that generate heat and electricity while being cost-effective, this technology will need a direct normal irradiance (DNI) of 5 kWh/m²/day [27].

It is best suited to places like the Middle East, Northern Africa, China, some of India, Southern Europe, the Southern United States, and Australia that receive a lot of sunlight, as well as many other places where people experience peak electricity problems, power outages, and rising electricity prices. A concentrated solar power system is an unending supply of energy and does not add to global warming. Depending on where it is on the planet, each square meter of concentrator surface for CSP systems can prevent 200–300 kilogram (kg) of carbon dioxide from being released into the atmosphere each year. In 2020, 148 million tons of CO₂ are anticipated to be saved annually using concentrated solar power, rising to 2.1 billion tons globally in 2050 [26]. Photovoltaic (PV) energy is the second use of solar electricity. Photovoltaic systems, which use solar energy, may generate electricity. PV cells directly convert solar radiation from the sun into electricity. PV technology and installed system types come in a variety. The photovoltaic (PV) modules available today include cadmium telluride, copper-indium-gallium-diselenide (CIGS), microcrystalline silicon, polycrystalline silicon (or multi-crystalline), and monocrystalline silicon solar cells [28]. These systems can offer clean electricity for little or substantial use. They are placed and producing electricity on workplaces, public buildings, residential communities, and commercial structures all around the world. As was already said, solar photovoltaic (PV) is a typical form of renewable energy source that may reduce the use of fossil fuels and the

emissions they produce, such as CO₂, SO₂, and NO_x. For every kilowatt-hour of power produced, PV systems may reduce CO₂ emissions by 0.53 kg. By 2030, the use of PV systems can cut emissions of 68,000 to 99,000 tons of NO_x, 126,000 to 184,000 tons of SO₂, and 69 to 100 million tons of CO₂. As a result, many dangerous illnesses will

become less common as NO_x and SO₂ levels decrease. By 2030, the number of heart attacks and other forms of asthma would decline by 490–720 and 320–470, respectively [29]. There are still many reasons to install and employ solar energy technology, even if fossil fuels still dominate the world economy's energy balance. In compared to other renewable energy sources, its sustainability makes it one of the most secure sources of energy available to any country. As was already said, it also creates little to no pollution and the least amount of emissions that contribute to global warming. It can lower energy-related GHG emissions over the next few decades, working in tandem with other renewable energy sources to lessen the consequences of climate change. Solar energy is limitless, renewable, and has a great deal of potential to protect communities from the fluctuating cost of fossil fuels. Humans face a well-known problem to their quality of life when there is no stable source of electricity or energy. This is so because the majority of activities rely on accessible and adequate energy to run their manufacturing systems. Off-grid electricity, solar water heating, and solar PV applications are only a few examples of solar energy technologies that are cost-competitive with other energy sources. Utilizing solar energy has drawn a lot of attention worldwide because of the global energy crisis and efforts to reduce harmful environmental effects. Technologies based on solar energy may assist humanity in a variety of ways.

B. Low efficiency of solar technologies:

The low performance and efficiency of solar systems has always been one of the key issues with solar technology [30]. Solar panels, which generate electricity from sunshine, are largely responsible for the efficiency of energy conversion. Practical solar energy systems are often inefficient. The efficiency of power generated by solar systems is the lowest and is significantly lower than that of other renewable (such as wind and hydropower) and nonrenewable technologies. Solar cells made on single-crystalline silicon (sc-Si) have a maximum efficiency of over 25%. Multi-crystalline silicon (mc-Si) solar cells have an efficiency of roughly 21% at the same time. Additionally, unlike technologies that use fossil fuels, the location and weather have an impact on the power production of solar energy systems [31]. The effectiveness of solar power systems often depends on a number of environmental conditions, including solar radiation, ambient temperature,

relative humidity, and wind speed at the site. Most solar systems, including photovoltaic modules, do not function under normal operating parameters in overcast and wet weather.

C. Lack of qualified engineers and skilled labors:

Other obstacles to the use of solar energy include technical difficulties, a lack of competent engineers and skilled workers, among others [32]. The lack of trained engineering support to execute maintenance chores and handle control failures is a problem that many developing nations share. Developing nations struggle with a lack of technical know-how to put these facilities in place. For instance, in Mexico, a lack of indigenous human resources is a major obstacle to utilizing the nation's enormous potential for the development of solar technology. There is a lack of specialized training for solar energy projects in many developing nations' universities, vocational schools, technical training facilities, and labor training facilities

D. Lack of social awareness and acceptance of solar technologies:

Other obstacles to the use of solar energy include technical difficulties, a lack of competent engineers and skilled workers, among others [32]. The lack of trained engineering support to execute maintenance chores and handle control failures is a problem that many developing nations share. Developing nations struggle with a lack of technical know-how to put these facilities in place. For instance, in Mexico, a lack of indigenous human resources is a major obstacle to utilizing the nation's enormous potential for the development of solar technology. There is a lack of specialized training for solar energy projects in many developing nations' universities, vocational schools, technical training facilities, and labor training facilities.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The performance of the entire PV system is affected by a variety of factors, some of which have a favorable impact on the output while others have a negative impact. It is also evident that several scholars have contributed to the study of the variables influencing PV panels, but they didn't concentrate on integrating all of those variables and instead each investigated a small subset of variables. These studies also didn't show the range of losses that may result from these causes. Therefore, this research incorporates all of the variables that might have a significant impact on the performance of the panel. It also illustrates the direct and quantitative impact of each variable on the performance of the PV panel by displaying a range of potential power losses for the PV panel. Additionally, it organizes the components into groups and subgroups that weren't previously discussed in other research, including environmental factors (external),

PV system factors (internal), PV system installation factors (operational), PV system cost factors (economic), and other random factors. The performance of the system is greatly influenced by each of those variables. As this paper incorporates the environmental factors, internal factors, installation and operational factors, economic factors, and other factors affecting the performance of PV panels, the results of this study can benefit both practitioners and researchers by removing the burden of having to search several studies for obtaining an overall idea about the factors affecting the performance of PV panels. Researchers can do in-depth research on those elements, how to enhance some of them, and how to address issues related to elements that have a detrimental impact on the performance of PV panels. Additionally, practitioners can create models and systems that can be tested experimentally to lessen the impact of the negative factors on the performance of PV panels, such as cleaning systems for PV panels, cost-reduction plans, maintenance plans, improving the efficiency of the components, such as inverters and batteries, and other procedures that take into consideration the factors mentioned in this study.

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